

The Laboratory of Life: Implications of Students Attitude on Social Studies in the 21st Century Society

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Abstract. The study explored teachers' views towards students' attitudes related to Social Studies subject and how they cope with it in the 21st-century classroom. This study employed a phenomenological research design to determine the experiences and perceptions of the eight (8) participants. The themes on students' attitudes toward social studies subjects were perceived lack of relevance, a copious amount of rote memorization, and a lack of interest in political or societal issues. Meanwhile, the themes of teachers' coping strategies were making social studies relevant, incorporating current events, and rationalization for the use of technology. Lastly, the educational management insights highlighted improving students' fact-checking abilities, encouraging an active learning environment, and cultivating local and global perspectives. These themes implied that flexible classrooms, collaborative spaces, and technology-equipped environments provide a more dynamic learning experience. Management may also ensure that the curriculum reflects local and global perspectives, incorporating diverse cultural content, international issues, and perspectives from different regions into the standard curriculum. Moreover, the results provided comprehensive data for future research with similar scope. This study may be published in a reputable research journal.

KEY WORDS

1. laboratory of life 2. students attitude 3. social studies 4. 21st-century classroom

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1. Introduction

The Araling Panlipunan curriculum is anchored on the aspirations of the Education for All 2015 and K-12 Philippine Basic Education Curriculum Framework. These aim to gain 21st Century skills and developed learners who are functionally literate and developed Filipino. In general, the Social Studies Curriculum such as Araling Panlipunan, aims to develop analytic, evaluative, responsible, productive, environment-friendly, patriotic, and humane citizens who possess broad world perspective and values on historical and social matters. The teaching of Social Studies powerfully and authentically begins with a deep knowledge and understanding of the subject and its unique goals. Social studies programs prepare students to identify, understand, and work to solve our diverse nation's challenges in an increasingly interdependent world. Education for citizenship should help students acquire and learn to use the skills, knowledge, and attitudes that will prepare them to be competent and respon-

sible citizens throughout their lives. Competent and responsible citizens are informed and thoughtful, participate in their communities, are involved politically, and exhibit moral and civic virtues (Guarin Salcedo, 2018). In Australia, the image of Social Studies as a practical curriculum component is less than desirable. In terms of the status of Social Studies, studies by Fraser (2020) reported that students ranked Social Studies well below the core subjects of English, Mathematics, and Science. While students may not like these subjects, they are perceived by students as being important subjects in gaining future employment and, therefore, essential subjects to study. Such negative and indifferent attitudes towards the subject are bound to affect student motivation to learn Social Studies. Since attitude may be causally related to achievement, the likely educational outcome would be reduced learning. Moreover, given the current economic situation and the greater accountability demanded of schools, unless corrected, this negative view might lead to a lack of support and diminished resources for Social Studies. With the move to greater flexibility in post-compulsory education, there is a possibility that fewer students will choose Social Studies in upper school, which will have a compounding effect on the status of Social Studies as a school subject (Darby, 2020). Previous research in Ghana, as cited by Teye (2019), indicates that young students are not optimistic about social studies. A study surveyed student attitudes towards social studies in the San Francisco Public Schools. They found that students in grades 9 to 12 ranked social studies last in importance compared to other core subjects such as English and mathematics. The participants described social studies as confusing and having little relationship to their future. Similarly, in the United States, as cited by Moroz (2019), students at all year levels were negative about social studies, growing increasingly disenchanted with it and with school in general. Social studies are

frequently shown to be the least-liked subject at both primary and secondary schooling. In fact, in a list of thirteen subjects, social studies ranked worse than all but religious education. In the Philippines, it has been noted for several years that the attitude toward learning in any discipline is critical; thus, it affects students' performance. In a typical Araling Panlipunan class, students show a lack of interest, poor participation, and lack of comprehension. Rayos (2019) emphasizes that these factors affect student academic performance. He even cited that academic performance among students in Araling Panlipunan is also a problem. Moreover, Escarlos, Tan, Bermillo, Magday, Capuyan, Ocier, and Palapar (2018) studied the performance of the 4th-year students' NAT in the two (2) Divisions of the Province Bukidnon. They found out that those areas with low mean percentage scores are competencies of higher-order thinking skills. These factors depend upon the kind of teacher-student interaction where supervision and flexibility become necessary to achieve academic accomplishment in Social Studies. Problems arise in teaching Araling Panlipunan subjects, such as acquiring skills in a specific topic or lesson. Araling Panlipunan teachers must learn to teach social studies standards to both special needs and general learners. However, no single technique, approach, or strategy will accomplish this because of the complex nature of the Araling Panlipunan. The complexity rests in the diverse nature of the Araling Panlipunan, the wide variety of Araling Panlipunan teachers, the range of learning problems held by learners in Araling Panlipunan classrooms, and the many differences among the social studies standards themselves. However, general areas of advice can be offered to point teachers in the right direction (Guarin Salcedo, 2018). It was observed that in Davao De Oro, Grade 10 students' attitude towards the subject was an issue of interest and engagement; many students were not interested in Social Studies for a number of

reasons, and traditionally, it is a subject that they either love or hate. Specifically, they find studying Social Studies boring and irrelevant to their future career. Most students see it as either discovering the past or memorizing dates. Teachers often depend upon textbooks and written materials to provide pupils with the basic knowledge to further their learning and participate actively in class discussions. Abad and Taperca (2018) identified that students' attitudes influence academic performance. A child's attitude toward a subject affects his knowledge about it. Corresponding to the gap mentioned earlier, the researcher intends to conduct a study on the perception of the teachers toward stu-

dents' attitudes related to Social Studies subject in 21st-century society. This study explores the attitudes of Grade 10 students in Manat National High School, Davao De Oro. This study will also dig into the coping strategies of teachers as it was noted that the type of students in the school today are technologically influenced and mentally and physically active. This study is also expected to give information to effectively plan action for improving teaching-learning in Araling Panlipunan/Social Studies subject. Appropriate materials and strategies should be provided to address their learning needs; otherwise, it may conceal their learning interest and potential.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study aimed to investigate teachers' perceptions of students' attitudes related to Social Studies subject and how they cope with it in the 21st-century classroom. This was a vital subject in the education system, designed to equip students with the knowledge and skills to understand and engage with society and the world around them. However, many teachers face an ongoing challenge in actively motivating students to participate and develop a positive attitude toward social studies. This study explored the reasons behind students' often lackluster approach and how teachers overcome this challenge.

1.2. Research Questions—The primary research questions of this study were the following:

- (1) What are your perceptions about students' attitudes toward social studies subjects?
- (2) How do teachers cope with the challenges of students' attitudes toward social studies in a 21st-century classroom?
- (3) What educational management insights are drawn from the experiences of teachers?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following terms were operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive. Social studies study man and his physical, social, political, cultural, and economic environment. It centers on man's development, how man influences his environment, and how the environment influences him in return. Students' Attitudes towards learning are important factors in the learners' levels of

goal setting, problem-solving abilities, beliefs about learning, inner and external motivations in the learning process, and academic performance. 21st-century learning involves developing a highly valuable skill set for the future. These skills were flagged as critical for the digital and evolving economy. Instead of specific subject knowledge, 21st-century skills are ways of thinking, ways of working, and ways of living.

1.4. Significant of the Study—To determine the outcomes of this study and to whom the findings are to be addressed, the following

persons or agencies were the beneficiaries. Department of Education. The Department of Education may use the research findings to iden-

tify gaps in the current social studies curriculum and make necessary improvements. Understanding the factors influencing students' attitudes can aid in developing a more relevant, engaging, and inclusive curriculum. Based on the research results, the department may develop targeted policies to enhance the teaching and learning of social studies. These policies may include teacher training programs, resource allocation, and strategies to promote positive attitudes among students. Principals. Principals may use the research outcomes to inform their school's strategic planning. Understanding the factors influencing students' attitudes can aid in devising targeted interventions and initiatives to improve social studies instruction and

student engagement. They may target support and professional development opportunities for teachers. This can help educators develop innovative teaching strategies that foster positive student attitudes. Teachers. Teachers may benefit from the research findings by adapting their teaching methods and strategies. Understanding what motivates and engages students can help teachers design lessons that cater to diverse learning styles and improve overall classroom participation. They may encourage more student-centered approaches, allowing students to explore topics of interest within the social studies subject, thereby enhancing their sense of ownership and motivation.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—The phenomenon of learning is so varied and diverse that its inclusion in eight single categories may not be warranted. Learning is a concept and not a 'thing'. The activity of learning is inferred only through behavioral symptoms. Kimble (1962) attempted to define learning as a relatively permanent change in behavioral potential resulting from reinforced practice. This definition postulates that the change needs not be an improvement. Addictions and prejudices are learned, as well as high-level skills and valuable knowledge. The psychological study of learning embraces more than learning a new job or academic subject. It also affects fundamental development, motivation, social behavior, and personality (as cited by Mensah, 2020). Learning development is revealed through the changing probability that an awaited behavior may result. He held the view that learning itself is not observable. Rather, It is an intervening variable that is inferred as a connecting process between an antecedent variable and consequent behavior. Hilgard (1962), inferring from Kohler's Theory of Insight Learning, stated that a learner is a resourceful person, one who is able to use what he

knows in new situations and one who is able to discover for himself solutions to problems that he has never before faced (as cited by Mensah, 2020). Insight learning encourages problem-solving behavior in the learner. The learner must be familiar with the essentials of the problem. For example, no one can solve a novel algebraic problem without knowing the meaning of the symbols and operations for which they stand. Insight learning requires the learner to see facts and understand the essentials of the problem. Insight learning depends upon the capacity of the learner. For example, older children can learn things younger children cannot. Past experiences influence this. All instances of learning involve the learner in a behavior of some sort. He learns to do something. An example is learning to read. The same behavior feature is exhibited by instances described as learning to become somebody. For example, one can learn to become a teacher. To learn to be somebody is to learn to do something. Learning involves the changing of one's behavior. From a variety of instances of learning, Thyme (1970) deduced Four Features of Learning Theory. In the first instance, the learner learns to do some-

thing. This, he interpreted as a feature of behavioral change. Secondly, he previously did something different. That is a change of behavior. The third feature is that behavior change occurs in a particular situation. Fourthly, the learner changes from one situation to another. In terms of these four features that appear to characterize learning, any instance of learning must get two responses: an old response and a new different response. That is, any instance of learning involves a two-fold series of behaviors. Thyme then defined learning as adopting a new response to a situation. This same learning can be applied in the teaching and learning of Social Studies. A fundamental implication of this definition is that learning is not a single 'thing.' On the contrary, it is a particular pattern or 'Gestalt' of behavior concerning some situation. Furthermore, this study is also based on Fleming's Visual-Auditory-Kinesthetic Theory of Learning Styles, as stated by Tenedero (2004), wherein learners were classified into three types: The VAK learning styles model suggests that most people can be divided into one of three preferred learning styles: the visual, auditory, and kinesthetic types. Someone with a visual learning style prefers to observe things, including pictures, diagrams, demonstrations, displays, handouts, films, flip charts, etc. These people will use phrases such as 'show me' and 'let us look at that' and will be best able to perform a new task after reading the instructions or watching someone else do it first. These are the people who will work from lists and written directions and instructions, take numerous detailed notes, tend to sit in the front, are usually neat and clean, often close their eyes to visualize or remember something, find something to watch if they are bored, like to see what they are learning, benefit from illustrations and presentations that use color, are attracted to written or spoken language rich in imagery, prefer stimuli to be isolated from auditory and kinesthetic distraction and finds passive surroundings

ideal (as cited by Agoyaoy, 2012). Someone with an Auditory learning style prefers transferring information through listening to the spoken word, of self or others, of sounds and noises. These people are happy being given spoken instructions over the telephone and can remember all the words to songs they hear. They sit where they can hear but need not pay attention to what is happening in front, may not coordinate colors or clothes, but can explain why they are wearing what they are wearing and why, hum or talk to themselves or others when bored, acquire knowledge by reading aloud, remember by verbalizing lessons to themselves (as cited by Agoyaoy, 2012). Someone with a Kinesthetic learning style prefers physical experience - touching, feeling, holding, doing, and practical hands-on experiences. These people like to experiment hands-on and never look at the instructions first. They need to be active and take frequent breaks, speak with their hands and with gestures, remember what was done but have difficulty recalling what was said or seen, find reasons to tinker or move when bored, and rely on what they can directly experience or perform activities such as cooking, construction, activity-making and art help them perceive, enjoys field trips and tasks that involve manipulating materials, sit near the door or someplace else where they can quickly get up and move around, uncomfortable in classrooms where they lack opportunities for hands-on experience and communicate by touching and appreciate physically expressed encouragement, such as a pat on the back (as cited by Agoyaoy, 2012). Understanding students' attitudes toward Araling Panlipunan/ Social Studies and their Teacher would greatly help in realizing the needs and problems of the teaching and learning process. Every student must develop the motivation to learn—the want-to—and couple this with the methods and materials for learning—the know-how and the know-why. The conceptual framework of the study is presented

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

in figure 1. Based on the figure, there are two interconnected variables. These variables are (1) perceptions about students' attitudes toward social studies subjects, (2) educational management insights drawn from the experiences of teachers, and (3) teachers coping with the challenges of students' attitudes towards social studies in a 21st century classroom.

2. Methodology

This chapter presented the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitated the consequent design and implementation, as elaborated in this chapter.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field of study. It establishes the background for the following conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types, which are elaborated below. *Ontology*. This part of the research pertained to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2022), the reality was subjective and multiple, as the study participants saw. The ontological issue addressed the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the perception of teachers toward students' attitudes related to Social Studies subject and how they cope with it in the 21st-century classroom was investigated. In this study, the researcher relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive

quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participant's answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. The responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal biases as the study progressed. Epistemology. This referred to the awareness of how knowledge claims were justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2022), stated that the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself and the participants on the epistemological assumption. He suggested that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an 'insider.' This study intended to gather information from the perception of teachers towards students' attitudes related to Social Studies subject and how they cope with it in the 21st-century classroom. It was assumed that

close interaction with the participants was established to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry. Axiology refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2022) averred that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. The researcher ensured the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understood the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpreted the answers in light of the participants' interpretation. Rhetoric. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher wrote in a literary, informal style using the personal voice, using qualitative terms and limited definitions. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person to elucidate Supreme Pupil Government (SPG) advisers on student leaders' servant leadership behavior.

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—The methodology was different from the method. Methodology is a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2019). In this study, the perception of teachers towards students' attitudes related to Social Studies subject and how they cope with it in the 21st-century classroom was investigated, particularly those teachers from Manat National High School, Nabunturan East District, Davao De Oro Division. The researcher's drive to know the deeper meaning of their experiences became the basis for qualitative research. It was considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underlie cultural symbols, personal experi-

ences, and phenomena." By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the teachers in a manner that, as David (2018) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences were presented. Phenomenological research was based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge; this experience was a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research is that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge. By analyzing how an event occurs in our daily lives, we can

learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into its nature (Morrissey Higgs, 2019). By doing phenomenology, which concerns the “what” and the “how” (Moustakas, 2020), the researcher projected that the subjective experi-

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design since it focused on the perception of teachers towards students’ attitudes related to Social Studies subject and how they cope with it in the 21st-century classroom. Creswell (2022), stressed phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research focused on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach is to describe the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread and were culled for phrases and themes grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, the researcher constructed the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2023) also added that phenomenology, with its roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, attempted to extract the purest, untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, the researcher used bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process. One method of bracketing is taking notes. According to Corbetta (2023), the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews provided in-depth methods that granted access to deep knowledge and explanations and helped grasp the subjects’ perspectives. Creswell (2022) also claimed that

ences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of the teachers were explored, and insights were drawn as a basis for possible future research and policy analysis in relation to this research.

qualitative research primarily used interviews. They occurred when researchers asked one or more participants general, open-ended questions and recorded their answers. Often, audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews were also helpful in following up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as further investigating their responses. In qualitative research, interviews were used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews was to understand the meaning of what the interviewees said (McNamara, 2020). Based on Quad’s (2019) statements, the researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer file to analyze it after the interview. Interviews were particularly useful for uncovering the story behind a participant’s experiences and pursuing in-depth information about a topic. The researcher collected data from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation, typically via long interviews. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation, extracting significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied up together to make a general description of the experience both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his or her meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written so that readers could better understand the essential, invariant structure of the essence

of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study were individuals who had experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his or her own experiences and observations, which was difficult. The researcher also needed to decide how and when his or her personal observations were incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectiv-

ity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. They were powerful tools for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study was to explore and assess teachers' perceptions of students' attitudes toward Social Studies and how they cope with it in the 21st-century classroom, the researcher intended to employ phenomenological methods of qualitative research.

2.4. Research Participants—The participants of this study were the eight (8) teachers of Manat National High School, Nabunturan East District, Davao De Oro Division. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: they must have been in their present position for at least 5 years, regardless of their age, sex, and marital status; they must have been teaching Araling Panlipunan/Social Studies sub-

jects for at least 5 years, regardless of their age, sex, and marital status; and they must have at least a very satisfactory rating in IPCRF. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2014). It was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings were authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations were significant in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues regarding the research participant in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations were specified as one of the most important parts of the research. The researcher needed to adhere to the aims of the research, imparting authentic knowledge, truth, and prevention of error. Social Value. The research was essential to society. In this study, the social value was focused on the experience of teachers. This study was explicitly conducted among the teachers. This study also served as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions from which classroom teachers could benefit. Thus, the social problem that

pushed the researcher's interest was teachers' perception of students' attitudes related to Social Studies subject and how they cope with it in the 21st-century classroom. Informed Consent. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2020), was adhered to. The invitation to the participants ensured that their participation in the research was completely voluntary in nature and was based on the understanding of adequate information. The recruitment and selection of participants are lodged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pillerin, 2021). All participants were given

an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter was to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the consent letter to the researcher before participating.

Vulnerability of Research Participants. The study participants could answer the research instrument, for they were all professional teachers in public schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that as the researcher, he or she could easily be reached through the contact number and be addressed in case there were some clarifications or questions concerning the study.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the chair of the panel or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. Furthermore, in the event that respondents experienced potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelled to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher had ensured that the respondents were safe during the conduct of the survey and interview. Thus, the distribution of the questionnaire was conducted in a safe venue and administered at their convenient time. The dominant concern of this study is the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality.

Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were considered to avoid a conflict of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information and representation of primary data findings in a biased way were avoided.

Justice. The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they had to give their full honesty in answering the survey questions, and additionally, any type of communication in relation to the research was done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they were the ones to benefit first from the study's results.

Transparency. The results of the study were accessed by the respondents heads of the participating schools because the information was available and was placed on CD or other storage devices which can be requested from the researcher to provide. In addition, by learning from the study results, participants were aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each participant was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they could be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview. This allowed the participants to amend or remove any information they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to use pseudonyms and change names and non-significant dates in the interest of protecting the participant's identity in all subsequent data analysis and reporting.

Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that he or she possessed the needed

qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher completed the academic requirements, passed the comprehensive examination prior to thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain the master's degree, and was qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study reached its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher strived that the study can be completed successfully in the specified time and that he or she is equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped enhance the paper by giving suggestions and recommendations for improving the study. Also, the researcher ensured that he or she had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, it was hoped that this study would be completed within the target time. Community Involvement. The researcher respected the respondents' lo-

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The researcher was responsible for uncovering, transferring, and exploiting knowledge to benefit educational institutions. To do so, the researcher took up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. The researcher conducted interviews with the participants and guided them in the process. The researcher interpreted ideas and responded based on existing literature and related studies and not on the researcher's knowledge, thoughts, and feelings to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in qualitative methods. The researcher implemented the qualitative method correctly. To do so, the researcher assessed himself and sought help from the research adviser and other professionals. These helped him demonstrate competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, and em-

cal traditions, culture, and views in this study. Moreover, this study did not involve any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in the recruitment of the participants or methods of data collection. Furthermore, the researcher necessarily expressed great pleasure in the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else had said his or her way. The researcher also used quotes to indicate that the text had been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty was present when working on the manuscript and that no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data or results was included, or that conclusions were purposefully put forward that were not accurate.

ploying Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. The researcher ensured different ways of making a record of what was said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and video recording. The recordings were transcribed verbatim before data analysis can begin. Records done by the researcher were adequately secured as they contained sensitive information and were relevant to the research. However, the data were being collected, and the researcher's primary responsibility was to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding were clearly articulated to participants and were approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research began. Analyst of data. The researcher saw the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. The researcher made sure that the

findings were accurate to the participants and that their voices were heard. The researcher organized and presented the data. The researcher presented the problem and the related literature and studies that supported it. The study's findings were presented, too, by the research ques-

2.7. Data Collection—The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. In September 2023, the researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher sent a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with Chapters 1 and 2 attached, together with the research instrument explaining the objectives of the study and the identification of the participants. The researcher waited for the SDS's response before conducting the study. Asking permission from the school heads. In the same month, after securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. Obtaining consent from the participants. In September 2023, the researcher asked permission from the participants. They were formally oriented about the study and the process they would undergo as participants. Conducting the interview. In September 2023, the researcher conducted an

2.8. Data Analysis—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews using Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2022), themes in qualitative research were similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization

tion, stating the results for each one by using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, the researcher gave future directions and implications of the study for improving educational policy and practices.

in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. The profile of the participants was taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. Transcribing the responses of the interviewees. In December 2023, the researcher transcribed the interviewees' responses precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it into English language. Data Coding and thematizing. In January 2024, after the transcription, the data were categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual data within the participants were compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants. Additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the participants to develop patterns and trends.

with the data was common to all forms of qualitative analysis. The researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with their data, reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis, involving generating pithy labels for essential features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis.

Coding was not simply a data reduction method; it was also an analytic process, so codes captured both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature

2.9. Framework of Analysis—The framework analysis of this research was flexible to allow the researcher to either collect all the data and then analyze it or do data analysis during the collection process. In the analysis stage, the gathered data was sifted, charted and sorted under key issues and themes. This involved a five-step process: (1) familiarization, (2) identifying a thematic framework, (3) indexing, (4) charting, and (5) mapping and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 2019). Familiarization refers to the process during which the researcher became familiarized with the transcripts of the data collected (i.e., interview or focus group transcripts, observation or field notes) and gained an overview of the collected data (Ritchie Spencer, 2019). In other words, the researcher became immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, studying the field, or reading the transcripts. Throughout this process, the researcher became aware of key ideas and recurrent themes and made a note of them. Due to the sheer volume of data collected in qualitative research, the researcher could not review all of the material. Thus, a selection of the data set was utilized. The selection depended on several aspects of the data collection process. For example, a mix of methods is used (e.g. interviews, documents, observations). The second stage, identifying a

of each theme and the relationship between the themes. Defining and naming themes: The researcher prepared a detailed analysis of each theme, identifying the ‘essence’ of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each theme. Writing up. This involved weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it about existing literature. The researcher made sure that the perspectives of teachers were presented comprehensively.

thematic framework, occurs after familiarization, when the researcher recognizes emerging themes or issues in the data set. These emerging themes or issues that had arisen from a priori themes were issues. However, at this stage, the researcher allowed the data to dictate the themes and issues. The researcher used the notes taken during the familiarization stage to achieve this end. The key issues, concepts, and themes that the participants had expressed now formed the basis of a thematic framework that was used to filter and classify the data (Ritchie Spencer, 2019). Indexing meant identifying portions or sections of the data that corresponded to a particular theme. This process was applied to all the textual data that had been gathered (e.g., transcripts of interviews). For convenience, Ritchie and Spencer recommend that a numerical system be used for the indexing references and annotated in the margin beside the text. Qualitative data analysis tools were ideal for such a task. The final stage, mapping, and interpretation, involved the analysis of the key characteristics as laid out in the charts. This analysis was able to provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, thus guiding the researcher in his/her interpretation of the data set. At this point, the researcher was cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis: “defining concepts, map-

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

ping range and nature of phenomena, creating typologies, finding associations, providing explanations, and developing strategies” (Ritchie and Spencer, 2019). Once again, these concepts, technologies, and associations reflected the participant. Therefore, any strategy or recommendations made by the researcher echoed the true attitudes, beliefs, and values of the participants.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The concepts of validity and reliability were relatively foreign to qualitative research. Instead of focusing on reliability and validity, qualitative researchers substituted data trustworthiness, which consisted of components such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Harts, 2020). Credibility involved establishing that the research findings were credible or believable from the participants’ perspectives. Observing the attributes of prolonged engagement is where credibility contributes to a belief in the trustworthiness of data. To address the credibility issue, the researcher interviewed as many research participants as possible or up to the point of saturation. Meanwhile, trans-

ferability was the degree to which the findings were generalized or transferred to other contexts. In this, the researcher did a thorough job in describing the relevant research context and assumptions. On the other hand, dependability was the consistency and repeatability of the research. The researcher made sure that the study’s findings were evaluated by the participants and scrutinized by an external reviewer. Lastly, conformability was the degree to which findings could be confirmed or corroborated by other researchers. The researcher documented the procedures and rechecked the data during the entire research process. The researcher also made sure that the findings were true and correct.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents and discusses the study's results concerning its aim. It also discusses the themes that emerged from the data gathered. The results present the description and background of the participants assigned pseudonyms to conceal their identities.

3.1. Perceptions of Students' Attitudes towards Social Studies Subjects—Social studies encompass various subjects, including history, geography, civics, economics, and sociology. These subjects play a pivotal role in shaping students into informed and responsible citizens who understand the historical context of societal issues, appreciate cultural diversity, and grasp the economic and political dynamics that shape their world. A positive attitude toward social studies is essential for students to develop critical thinking skills, empathy, and a sense of civic responsibility (Smith Johnson, 2018). However, students' attitudes towards social studies vary widely and are influenced by many factors. This section delves into the perceptions of students' attitudes toward social studies subjects. The teachers' responses were narrowed down into one to generate themes and subthemes. These were carefully analyzed and formulated based on informants' accounts and reflections.

3.1.1. Perceived lack of relevance—One of the primary reasons for students' disinterest in social studies is the perceived lack of relevance to their lives. Students often fail to recognize the practical implications of historical events or global issues, leading them to question the value of the subject in their daily existence. When social studies curricula fail to incorporate diverse perspectives and cultural contexts, students may struggle to relate to the material. This cultural dissonance contributes to a perception of irrelevance, especially for students whose backgrounds are not adequately represented in the curriculum. The responses of the participants validate the findings of Rogayan and Villanueva (2019) that Social studies often introduce abstract concepts, historical events, and geopolitical issues that might seem detached from students' immediate experiences. This disconnection can lead to a sense of irrelevance, with students questioning the practical application of the knowledge acquired. The subject has a broader scope in different sub-disciplines, and many teachers struggle with the lack of students' interest in the content. This lack of interest translates into a lack of motivation to learn, and so students seem uninterested and perceive it as a boring subject and irrelevant. Several pieces of literature reflect students' disinterest in social studies. Additionally, the changing educational landscapes and Education 4.0 add to the challenges the present social studies curriculum faces. When a teacher fails to convey the importance of Social Studies to the students, it results in negative attitudes among the students and less appreciation toward the subject matter; typically, a professor or a teacher would just stand in front of all the students and start reciting all the details of the topics. The scenario is that the teacher prioritizes finishing the lesson content, which leads learners to make sense of what is presented rather than memorizing all the dates, places, and names of prominent people and events (Dinc 2019).

3.1.2. A copious amount of rote memorization—Social studies, a rich and multidisciplinary field, is often perceived by students as a subject entailing copious amounts of rote memorization. This perception stems from traditional teaching methods prioritizing memorizing facts

and dates rather than fostering a deep understanding of historical events, cultural dynamics, and societal structures. Students may view social studies as a tedious chore, lacking the intellectual stimulation and curiosity that should accompany the exploration of human history and society. Some educational systems emphasize rote memorization of dates, names, and events, reducing social studies to a mundane exercise of memorizing facts rather than fostering critical thinking and analytical skills. This approach fails to stimulate students' curiosity and creativity. While it's important to know facts and dates, Trofanenko (2020) believes history teachers should challenge students, especially high school students, to think like historians. The

3.1.3. Lack of interest in political or societal issues—In education, social studies serve as a crucial foundation for developing informed, responsible, and engaged citizens. However, a prevailing challenge teacher participants face is the apparent lack of interest among students in political and societal issues within the social studies curriculum. The participants affirmed that the intricate nature of political and societal issues and their complexity can overwhelm students. The vast array of global challenges may lead to a sense of hopelessness, discouraging active engagement. A negative attitude towards the subject can lead to a lack of interest in political and societal issues, ultimately affecting the democratic fabric of society. Typical explanations for the lack of interest in politics and societal issues include young people's belief that it lacks relevance or their preoccupation with other interests and concerns. Indeed, it was often said that young people are preoccupied with other interests and activities that dominate their lives and leave little time to devote to such issues. Other studies point to the complexity of politics and young people's difficulties in understanding political and societal life and processes. Except for work carried out, young peo-

ple have also been found to hold politicians in low esteem, lacking trust in them or respect for them. This, too, is identified as a disincentive to becoming interested in politics and societal issues (as cited by White, Bruce and Ritchie, 2020). Scholars such as Biesta (2019), who facilitate students' education, should pay great attention to student individuality by allowing their values to matter and not always predetermining the answers. However, this does not mean that students should only give their own opinions on societal and political affairs; they should rather meet others' opinions and experience opposition towards their own worldviews. Progressing towards becoming an emancipated individual is not merely a process that is gone through by an individual; it requires plurality and difference. Teachers' most important task is to allow students to express themselves and experience challenges from their peers' perspectives. Where education only gives the accepted answers and does not allow students to be recognized as independent and capable, it limits itself to qualifying and socializing for an existing societal order. The figure above shows the emerging themes on the perceptions of students' attitudes toward social studies subjects. The themes were

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Fig. 3. Emerging Themes on the Perceptions of Students' Attitude on Social Studies Subjects

perceived as lack of relevance, copious amount of rote memorization, and lack of interest in political or societal issues. These themes implied that students may struggle to understand the significance of historical events, societal structures, and political processes, limiting their ability to

analyze and interpret complex issues. Hence, attention to students' psychological well-being, fostering a positive learning environment, and addressing individual needs are crucial for overall academic success.

3.2. Teachers Coping with the Challenges of Students' Attitude Towards Social Studies in a 21st Century Classroom—Social studies provides a platform for students to understand and engage with real-world issues. In a rapidly changing world, an appreciation for social studies is essential for cultivating informed and responsible global citizens who can contribute to addressing societal challenges. Coping with the challenges in social studies education allows teachers to prioritize critical thinking over rote

memorization. This shift is crucial for preparing students to analyze complex issues, make informed decisions, and develop the problem-solving skills needed in the 21st century. This section percent teachers' coping strategies with the challenges of students' attitudes towards social studies in a 21st-century classroom. The teachers' responses were narrowed down into one to generate themes and subthemes. These were carefully analyzed and formulated based on informants' accounts and reflections.

3.2.1. Making social studies relevant—Making social studies relevant is a powerful strategy in teaching the subject, as it enhances student engagement, encourages critical think-

ing, and facilitates a deeper understanding of the world. When students perceive the relevance of social studies to their lives, communities, and the broader global context, they are more likely

to be motivated and actively participate in their learning. The participants claim that when students see the direct connections between social studies concepts and their lives, they become more engaged in learning. Relevant content captures their interest and curiosity, making the subject matter more appealing. The responses of the participants validates the findings of Zhao Hoge (2005) that the field of social studies education repeatedly must provide students with practice in decision-making and higher-order thinking skills, so they become interested in and connected to what is being taught. Teachers must challenge students to think more deeply by using their higher-order questions. Many researchers suggest that a crucial factor for history teachers to consider is how to deliver the subject material in a manner that is relevant to students' lives and has a high degree of rigor. Students need to have opportunities to think critically or

conceptualize and apply information assembled from observation or experience to derive meaning from an increasingly pluralistic society. To this point, Blanchard et al. (2023) contend that unless social studies education speaks to the genuine complexities that young people experience, students are tempted to consider school irrelevant to the real issues in their lives. Many scholars assert that students must be able to define a relationship between the curriculum and the world in which they live. Establishing relevance could be initiated by showing how concepts can be applied in practice, relating content to local cases or everyday applications, or finding applications of learned concepts in current newsworthy issues. Relevance can pique curiosity and focus student attention. According to the findings of Alazzi and Chiodo (2023), students' interests were positively impacted when relevancy was demonstrated.

3.2.2. Incorporating current events— Present-day newsworthy material helps students to contextualize the content of the social science class. Students can connect real-time issues to historical situations, thereby employing higher-order or critical thinking skills to demonstrate that history can be a living discipline undertaken through the study of events that are presently unfolding. According to the participants, the connection of contemporary and historical topics can assist in students' awareness of how major events are related to one another in time and the ability to distinguish between cause and effect about historical events. Similarly, students would increase their ability to explain the sources of historical continuity and how the combination of ideas and events explains the emergence of new patterns. The responses of the participants corroborate the studies of Anderman and Johnson (2021), which state that incorporating current events can elevate academic achievement and motivation. Their

study of current events was associated with increased students' completion of assigned tasks, not just for the extrinsic motivation of the grade assigned but also due to an increased interest in learning. They also postulated that schools could provide a context for practicing news-seeking behaviors. Their results also indicated that the students' application in news-seeking behaviors at school relates to the transference of the same newsgathering practices at home. Additionally, news knowledge correlated to greater student self-efficacy and depth of thinking about the news. These findings are significant because they demonstrate that the study of current events in school helps promote competent citizens outside of school who can engage critically in the world. While learning history aids comprehension of one's place in the world, studying past and present events provides a framework for observing the roles individuals, groups, institutions, and governments play in shaping society (as cited by Logan, 2011).

3.2.3. *Rationalizing the use of technology*—According to the participants, one of the notable contributions of technology to social studies education is the advent of interactive learning platforms. These platforms offer immersive experiences that transport students to different historical periods or geographic locations. Virtual tours, interactive maps, and multimedia resources allow students to explore ancient civilizations, dissect historical events, and witness the consequences of societal changes. Such tools bridge the gap between theoretical concepts and tangible experiences, making social studies come alive in the classroom. Moreover, the participants attest that technology keeps social studies education relevant by providing access to real-time data and current events. Teacher participants incorporate up-to-date information into their lessons, demonstrating the dynamic nature of social, political, and economic landscapes through technology. This enhances students' awareness of contemporary issues and encourages them to connect historical patterns to present-day events, fostering critical thinking and a sense of civic responsibility. Online and digital technologies have been used increasingly as a resource to mitigate the limits of time and increase student engagement and achievement. Zhao's (2023) study confirms both uses and describes teachers' perceptions of technology integration with two terms: efficiency-oriented and enhancement-oriented views. Technology can be seen as a tool to facilitate paperwork and obtaining information more efficiently or integrate technology to enhance classroom instruction and student learning. As Taylor and Duran (2020) contend, meeting the demands of teaching in the digital age requires identifying effective types of educational technology and ways of encouraging its use. This section pertains to research surrounding the skills students must develop as they evolve into citizens of the digital age. Taylor and Duran (2020) investigated the use of technology by social science educators. They found that student achievement in history increases when technology is used, and students were more interested in researching after exploring electronic sources. Students must distinguish relevant from irrelevant information, essential from incidental information, and verifiable from unverifiable information. Many have argued that for citizens of this century, the ability to differentiate relevant from irrelevant information is crucial due to the magnitude of data available in this information age. Figure 4 above shows the emerging themes of teachers' coping strategies with the challenges of students' attitudes toward social studies in a 21st-century classroom. The themes were making social studies relevant, incorporating current events, and rationalizing the use of technology. These themes implied that teachers adopting them may help their students recognize their role in a globalized world, fostering cultural awareness, empathy, and a sense of responsibility towards diverse societies. These themes cultivate critical thinking as students are prompted to analyze, question, and evaluate information in the context of real-world issues. In addition, with the integration of technology, teachers can address diverse learning styles. Multimedia resources, interactive platforms, and technology-based activities cater to different preferences, ensuring a more inclusive and accessible learning environment. Hence, Teachers adopting may find engaging in ongoing professional development beneficial. Staying abreast of the latest educational technologies, pedagogical approaches, and strategies for making social studies relevant ensures teachers are well-equipped to meet the evolving needs of 21st-century learners.

3.3. *Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Experiences of the Teachers*—

Fig. 4. Emerging Themes on Teachers Coping with the Challenges of Students' Attitude Towards Social Studies in a 21st Century Classroom

This section presents the participants' educational management insights. Their responses were narrowed down into one to generate themes and subthemes. These were carefully analyzed and formulated based on informants' accounts and reflections.

3.3.1. Improving students' fact-checking abilities—In an era characterized by a deluge of information, teaching students the art of fact-checking has never been more critical, especially in social studies. The participants defined fact-checking as verifying the accuracy of information in digital media. For them, logical reasoning accompanied by correct information must be developed as it is one of the essential skills for effective learning. Logical reasoning ability has a great influence on how students identify fake news, as logic is always reasonable and requires a person's deeper understanding of any situation. Fact-checking is a cornerstone of media literacy, an increasingly vital skill in today's digital age. Social studies classrooms become hubs for teaching students how to scrutinize written texts and evaluate images, videos, and other forms of media. Media literacy becomes an indispensable asset for responsible

and informed citizenship in an environment saturated with visual information. Students must rely primarily on news content and limited information relevant to society and face multiple challenges to detect false news during its life span at an early stage. Students may adapt and become less vulnerable to dissemination if they become aware of fake news on social media. Students should be encouraged to share news and information that can affect their social life. Early media literacy will help empower students against the risk of disinformation and may be the best prevention (Roozenbeek Van Der Linden, 2018). Traditionally, fact-checking lessons involved "vertical" reading, where students systematically explore and critique elements within a source. Many students are familiar with and have used checklists based on vertical reading to determine whether a piece of information is credible, such as assessing the source's author-

ity, purpose, accuracy, currency, and relevance. However, verifying a source through vertical reading can be difficult in the digital age, as some internet sites are deliberately designed to be misleading. Additionally, now that most students can access online information, they should not be restricted to vertical reading. Instead, current recommendations suggest teaching to read

3.3.2. Encouraging an active learning environment—One of the primary advantages of cultivating an active learning environment in social studies is the heightened level of student engagement. Active learning methods, such as group discussions, debates, and interactive projects, invite students to explore historical narratives and contemporary societal issues actively. This active engagement captures their interest and nurtures a genuine curiosity about the world around them. The participants' response corroborates with Logan (2019), who states that teaching is often a creative act that must respond to the diverse needs of the student population within each classroom. Students with positive experiences with their teacher and in the classroom tend to report more positive attitudes toward history and social science. When teachers

3.3.3. Cultivating local and global perspectives—The participants claim that one of the goals of teaching social studies is to cultivate students' global vision and raise students' interest in world affairs. For them, it is essential to integrate not just the local and national aspects but also the global affairs so that students would have diverse ideas on culture, traditions, economy, environmental protection, politics, and more and for them to evaluate the shared information. Scholars have stated the importance of fostering global citizens who understand the world around them and are prepared to engage

laterally, that is, by examining other sources and triangulating findings. This involves validating a target source using six steps: investigate the source's author, perform keyword searches, verify information and quotations, research citations, look up organizations cited, and analyze sponsorship or ads (Walsh-Moorman et al., 2020).

employ instructional techniques that garner students' attention, such as learning activities that provide interaction with peers, in-depth investigation, and opportunities to construct meaning from their own experiences, students' attitudes toward and subsequent interest in history are increased. Larson and Keiper (2020) describe discussion as an active learning activity because it develops higher-order thinking skills, enabling students to interpret, analyze, and manipulate information. Students explain their ideas and thoughts rather than merely recount or recite memorized facts and details. During discussion, learners are not passive recipients of information from a teacher. Instead, learners are active participants. Discussions require students to organize available information to arrive at their defensible answers when combined with probing, open-ended questions.

responsibly in problems of international significance. According to the Partnership for 21st Century Learning (2019), global competence is critical for innovation, and students need to develop the sensibilities to advance solutions that will impact later generations. One way this can be accomplished is through intentional teaching practices. Digital innovations and increased access to connected devices and tools have improved the possibility of engaging with people and places beyond the immediate borders. Hence, educators need to rethink their teaching approaches, including considering and

Fig. 5. Emerging Themes on the Educational Management Insights drawn from the Experiences of the Teachers

promoting new ways of connecting, collaborating, thinking, and creating beyond the classroom. Noddings (2020) believes that these skills are needed for students to make well-reasoned judgments about the information they receive about global issues. Students should learn to look at numerical data carefully and ask about the source of the figures. In short, they should be encouraged to dig more deeply behind the figures to analyze information correctly. He also argues that students should value global differences in opinions and attitudes. The figure above shows the emerging themes on the educational management insights drawn from the experiences of the participants. The themes were

improving students’ fact-checking abilities, encouraging an active learning environment, and cultivating local and global perspectives. These themes implied that educational management may consider redesigning learning spaces to accommodate active learning. Flexible classrooms, collaborative spaces, and technology-equipped environments contribute to a more dynamic learning experience. Management may also ensure that the curriculum reflects local and global perspectives, incorporating diverse cultural content, global issues, and perspectives from different regions into the standard curriculum.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a brief overview of the study followed by implications based on its findings. Future directions in the participants’ experiences are also discussed here

4.1. Findings—The study was intended to identify teachers’ reactions to students’ attitudes toward Social Studies in the framework

of globalization and how they address this in 21st-century classrooms. The results revealed that students usually perceived Social studies

as unnecessary stuff that was only presented to them to be memorized and that they do not like it much, especially about political and societal issues. One of the significant effects of this picture was that people would lose their engagement, no longer be motivated, and would not develop critical thinking skills or civic awareness. To counter some students' negativity towards the subject, incorporating real-world examples, exercises from current events, and practical applications need to be considered. Educators must apply active teaching strategies based on science inquiry for students' scientific exploration. Finally, when technology is combined with present events in the curriculum, it helps the students to see themselves in a globalized

4.2. Implications—This study aimed to investigate teachers' perceptions of students' attitudes toward Social Studies and how they cope with them in the 21st-century classroom. The emerging themes regarding students' attitudes toward social studies subjects were perceived lack of relevance, copious rote memorization, and lack of interest in political or societal issues. These themes implied that encouraging curiosity, exploration, and a passion for understanding the world can contribute to a positive attitude toward continuous learning. Social studies education should strive to cultivate cultural competence and global awareness, preparing students for an interconnected and diverse world. Perceived lack of relevance and excessive rote memorization may lead to decreased student engagement and motivation. They may disengage from the learning process, negatively impacting their academic performance and overall attitude toward education. In addition, rote memorization often hinders the development of critical thinking and analytical skills. Students may struggle to understand the significance of historical events, societal structures, and political processes, limiting their ability to analyze and inter-

world. This helps to develop cultural understanding and empathy and to make informed citizenship. Well-trained teachers can only be successful if ongoing professional development is provided to them so that they stay updated with the most recent educational technologies and the best pedagogical approaches. When it comes to educational management, fact-checking training should be available, students should be encouraged to be actively involved, and the local and global aspects should be incorporated. Turning learning spaces into active learning spaces and making the curriculum more diverse, which would be a matter of good reflection, would help create a dynamic and multicultural learning environment.

pret complex issues. A lack of interest in political or societal issues may contribute to a deficit in civic awareness and participation. They may be unprepared to participate in civic activities, make informed decisions, or contribute meaningfully to their communities. Curriculum developers were being called to incorporate real-world examples, current events, and practical applications to enhance the relevance of social studies content. Moreover, Educators should explore more interactive and student-centered teaching approaches that foster critical thinking, curiosity, and a genuine interest in the subject matter. Meanwhile, the emerging themes on teachers' coping strategies with the challenges of students' attitudes towards social studies in a 21st-century classroom were making social studies relevant, incorporating current events, and rationalizing the use of technology. These themes implied that teachers adopting them may help their students recognize their role in a globalized world, fostering cultural awareness, empathy, and a sense of responsibility towards diverse societies. These themes cultivate critical thinking as students are prompted to analyze, question, and evaluate information in the con-

text of real-world issues. In addition, the combination of incorporating current events and making social studies relevant contributes to fostering informed citizenship. Students become more aware of societal issues, political dynamics, and historical contexts, empowering them to participate in civic responsibilities and make informed decisions actively. Also, with technology integration, teachers can address diverse learning styles. Multimedia resources, interactive platforms, and technology-based activities cater to different preferences, ensuring a more inclusive and accessible learning environment. Hence, teachers adopting these methods may find engaging in ongoing professional development beneficial. Staying abreast of the latest educational technologies, pedagogical approaches, and strategies for making social studies rele-

vant ensures that teachers are well-equipped to meet the evolving needs of 21st-century learners. Lastly, the educational management insights drawn from the participants' experiences focused on improving students' fact-checking abilities, encouraging an active learning environment, and cultivating local and global perspectives. These themes implied that educational management may consider redesigning learning spaces to accommodate active learning. Flexible classrooms, collaborative spaces, and technology-equipped environments create a more dynamic learning experience. Management may also ensure that the curriculum reflects local and global perspectives, incorporating diverse cultural content, global issues, and perspectives from different regions into the standard curriculum.

4.3. Future Directions—Data obtained had future directions for various educational stakeholders, including policymakers, administrators, and teachers. The future directions of this study were as follows: Policymakers may focus on fostering curriculum innovation in social studies. They may regularly update curricula to reflect contemporary issues, diverse perspectives, and global interconnectedness. Policies may be developed to support the seamless integration of technology in social studies education, including providing access to digital resources, teacher professional development, and equitable access to technology for all students. School Principals may encourage collaboration between social studies and other disciplines, fostering interdisciplinary projects and initiatives. Principals may also develop strategies to enhance community engagement in social studies education, such as involving parents, local experts, and community members in projects, discussions, and events that connect the classroom with the broader community. Teachers may continually adapt to emerging technologies, staying

informed about the latest tools and incorporating them into their teaching strategies. They may also explore and implement personalized learning pathways, allowing students to explore areas of interest within the social studies curriculum and pace their learning according to individual needs. Moreover, future researchers may delve into the efficacy of inquiry-based learning in social studies or investigate innovative assessment strategies that measure 21st-century social studies skills. These recommended studies will yield advantageous findings and implications tailored to the organization and hierarchical context of the education sector. The recommendations below were to be considered in addressing the difficulties encountered in the study relative to the student's disposition toward social sciences. While developing a curriculum, one may highlight examples from the real world and events and apply them to reality to improve the link between social studies and everyone's daily life. This approach helps students turn from material recall to the subject's social relevance. Educators are stimulated to involve students in con-

textual activity-oriented challenges, techniques that encourage students to think critically and get curious about the subject. Incorporating current events, technology, and flexibility in different learning styles will channel inclusiveness, generating a more inclusive educational environment. For example, in scenario studies, teachers could use international topics like climate change meetings (these topics should also be in the history curriculum), connecting them with historical events and social influences. This process enables the students to progress from fact memorization to realizing the social role of the one. Teachers were advised to incorporate contextual, activity-targeted challenges as the foundations of education for students. One example is that creating debates on current political issues or the facsimile of historical events triggers thinking and questions. Also, introducing technology, such as using virtual reality to walk around ancient excavations or online platforms for group work, helps to match different learning styles. It, therefore, allows all participants to work together as a team. Moreover, teachers may dedicate time to regular professional development to keep up with changing educational technologies and use the best teaching methods. For instance, this may encompass mere participation in workshops devoted to AI integration or engagement in online courses about innovative teaching approaches. They could directly connect the necessitated learning requirements of this century with what was provided generationally. Furthermore, information acquisition, credit-checking, and employing active learning strategies are essential. Instructional leaders need to shift their perspective concerning learning spaces and treat them as places that transpose traditional classroom confines. For instance, the availability of laptops, Internet-based learning resources, and movable furniture to create group workspaces and interactive sessions with fellow students could enhance the learning process. The culture of the local, along with the spread of international education, can be achieved through writing the history and the current global issues like the effect of diseases on a global level and relations into the trade are some of the factors that would ensure that students live in a community that was integrated. Therefore, the varied strategies are purposefully designed to induce an aware community adept at critical thinking. Moreover, it can coexist in a heterogeneous and heterogeneous learning process.

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